

Familial Relationships of Photographic Doubles

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In recent years, the vocabulary of the historians of photography has started to feature the term “practices”. We are no longer interested only in the origin of photographs – how, where and why they came into existence, who created them, which material or process was involved, what possibilities the photographers had at their disposal in a particular period of time, how to interpret a particular photograph, and what part it played in the context of art or communication. With the growing dominance of sensory methodology in the history of photography and the increasing attention devoted to the photographic object, we tend to be more interested in the everyday practice of photographic studios and photographers, as well as in practices linked with further stages in the existence of specific photographs, both in the sense of objects and images. We are interested in the “daily lives” of photographs: what they have been through, how they were treated, what role they played over time, how and why they were interpreted, recycled, what values and meanings they were progressively assigned, and so on.

In other words, we are not solely interested in the nature of photographs – their origin, ideal state or the theoretical possibilities and prerequisites which can be derived from period newspaper, manuals, address books and patent applications, which might or might not have been relevant in each case. We are equally interested in the nurture of photographs – the circumstances surrounding their existence, the potential and practice of particular photographers, publishers and collectors which are often miles away from theory or the ideal state.

In my opinion, an excellent means to study these practices, and especially the nurture, are duplicates or doubles; as with twin studies – which, through research into identical twins, strive to find out whether a person’s character or, for example, a mental illness is mostly due to genetic heritage or to the environment and education. In contrast to twin studies, the history of photography is not bothered by the classic dilemma of nature versus nurture; nonetheless, there exist at least three interesting parallels or similarities between these two categories. 1) Duplicates are impossible to overlook, they never fail to attract our attention, regardless of whether they trigger positive or negative reactions (in the case of photographs the latter mainly in situations involving overflowing storage rooms). The existence of duplicates can be hardly ignored, be it from the position of the photo-collection curator or the author of a publication. 2) When noticing duplicates, in the initial phase we centre on the similarities, on the basic “genetic makeup” – nature; we want to see in what ways they are identical. 3) We only start looking at the differences in the next phase, when we also start looking for the causes of them.

Naturally, this provokes the question of what a duplicate actually is. There are various definitions, for example, “almost identical copies”, “multiple originals” or “identical strangers” (for the fans of last year’s documentary by Tim Wardle about The Triplets). Needless to say, an ideal, or at least less vague, definition would be hard to find. The term “duplicate” is rather broad and sometimes it is difficult to decide what remains a duplicate and what is no longer a duplicate, even when looking at specific photographs: some photographs appear identical at first glance, yet on closer observation it becomes clear that they are two different shots – copies from two different negatives (fig. 1); and in contrast, it might emerge that two seemingly completely different photographs are of identical origin (fig. 2).

Fig. 1 Andreas Groll, Prague, Old Town Hall, 1856, salt print, IAH CAS, inv. no. 573 (left); Andreas Groll, Prague, Old Town Hall, 1856, albumen print, IAH CAS, inv. no. 574 (right)

Rahmen - aus der früheren Spengler'schen Sammlung

Fig. 2 Unknown photographer, A wooden frame from the former Spengler collection, 1870s (?), albumen prints, Moravian Gallery in Brno, Archive collection, (both) s. n. (cropped)

Owing to the variability and scope of photographic procedures, materials, technologies and the work of the individual photographers, it is virtually impossible to produce an ideal, generally valid definition. In fact, the definitions of duplicates are usually more or less intuitive. The situation is further complicated by the fact that the majority of photographs are indeed duplicates, be it, figuratively speaking, in the “vertical” sense or in the “horizontal” one: photographs are basically serial products, not in the terms of the reproducibility of the photographic image, but simply because they typically originate in series. Only very exceptionally does one come across a photographic only child (more probably it would be an orphan), which also holds true of unique items such as daguerreotypes (fig. 3).

In my paper, I would like to point out two areas in which duplicates play an important part: the first one is research into the history of photography, and the second one is the work of curators.

Fig. 3 Wilhelm Horn, Landowner Marie Kodůusková, ca. 1849, daguerreotypes, left: National Museum, Prague, inv. no. [H2-18 6953](#), right: Prague City Museum, inv. no. [H 019 942](#)

Research

Photographic duplicates have an undeserved reputation for being needless, boring and replaceable, despite the fact that they are virtually perfect and very often also the only direct sources for research into the history of photography, especially if one is interested in practices. It is thanks to them that we can trace not only the practice of a particular photographer or studio, sometimes within the scope of several decades, but also the history of the individual photographs, the practice of publishers and conservators, the interests and preferences of owners and others who have handled the photographs.

One situation in which an encounter with duplicates is unavoidable is the preparation of publications of the catalogue raisonné type. I would like to demonstrate the potential of duplicates in the context of research into the history of photography on the example of one such catalogue. It is a book dedicated to the earliest period of photographing Prague, notably the years 1850 through 1870, which was published in 2019 by the Prague City Museum, in collaboration with the Prague City

Archives and the Institute of Art History of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IAH CAS) (fig. 4).¹ In the course of material research preceding the publication, over 2,000 photographic objects had been found, most of them in the collections of the three mentioned institutions which hold the largest corpuses of photographs of Prague from the 19th century. Approximately 700 photographs were selected for the book. Duplicates found for these photographs within a predefined area of collections and institutions, are listed in the catalogue section of the book. In most cases, two or three duplicates were identified, yet sometimes there were as many as more than ten objects.

Fig. 4 Kateřina Bečková – Miroslava Píkrlová – Petra Trnková, Nejstarší fotografie Prahy / The Earliest Photographs of Prague 1850–1870, Prague 2019, book cover (left), catalogue sample (right).

The existence of a relatively large number of duplicates in such a small area can be explained by the fact that these are chiefly photos of historical architecture, the content of which did not become too outdated for quite a while; many of them remained on the market for several decades. Both in the book and in the history of photographing Prague in general, an exclusive position is held by two photographers: Andreas Groll (1812–1872) from Vienna and Prague photographer František Fridrich (1829–1892). Their careers are relatively well traced;² in addition, with Groll we now also know about his working “practices” in detail. To a large extent, this is just thanks to duplicates, or due to the technical flaws and anomalies which they display and which become more and more obvious as time passes. Groll’s photographs show very well how they were modified and retouched; how Groll’s technique, taste, quality standards, cataloguing system and distribution changed in the course of time (fig. 5). We learn about his clients, the destinies of the photographs etc.³

¹ Kateřina Bečková – Miroslava Píkrlová – Petra Trnková, Nejstarší fotografie Prahy / The Earliest Photographs of Prague 1850–1870, Prague 2019.

² Jiří Koliš ed., František Fridrich: The Prominent Photographer of the 19th-Century Prague, Prague 2018. – Monika Faber ed., Andreas Groll. Wiens erster moderner Fotograf 1812–1872, Vienna – Salzburg 2015.

³ Petra Trnková, The Unbearable (and Irresistible) Charm of “Duplicates”, in Julia Bärnighausen, Costanza Caraffa, Stefanie Klamm, Franka Schneider, and Petra Wodtke eds., Photo-Objects: On the Materiality of Photographs and Photo Archives, Berlin 2019, pp. 245–260 [<http://mprl-series.mpg.de/studies/12/15/index.html>].

Fig. 5 Andreas Groll, Prague, Old Town Hall, 1856, salt prints / albumenized salt prints / albumen prints, IAH CAS, inv. nos. 572–579

František Fridrich’s photographs, preserved in larger quantities and – “regrettably” – mostly in better condition, have similar potential. Fridrich’s career took off in the late 1850s and the early 1860s, that is roughly a decade after Groll started. In Prague he photographed similar motifs and compositions, sometimes from the same viewpoints as Groll, but for a different kind of clientele. While Groll’s shots were chiefly purchased by architects, art historians, heritage care specialists and museum institutions, Fridrich’s photographs attracted the attention of a much wider audience. This corresponded to their overall rendering and format, as well as the larger production volume and much more consistent technical quality. Yet even in this case duplicates provide information about the run of the company for which there are no other sources. This regards, for example, the technical equipment. Fridrich was an efficient photographer and in the course of several years became also a major businessman who was clearly the most productive Prague photographer, distributing his output through a network of contacts even beyond Europe. The more-or-less natural notion of a photographer who only lives for his work and never makes a move without his camera is somewhat undermined by Jakob Wothly’s (1823–1873) recollection. This German photographer and inventor arrived in Prague in spring 1865, and during his time there visited several local photographic enterprises and met their owners. Although he did not get to meet Fridrich, he later caught a glimpse of him on a Sunday promenade and “noted with satisfaction that the equipage of photographer Fridrich, both the horses and the liveries of his servants, were among the most tasteful I saw that evening”.⁴

The most spectacular photographs from Fridrich’s production include panoramas, folded objects consisting of several large-format shots, and partly a small number of panoramic photos of Old Town Square held, for example, by the [Austrian National Library](#) and the Prague City Museum. Yet for none of them a panoramic camera was employed. The duplicates of the shots of Old Town Square which are in the IAH collection show that the photos were taken with the use of a wide-angle lens on

⁴ [Jakob Wothly], *Aus dem Tagebuche eines Wiener Photographen. Photographische Reisebilder*. Berliner photographische Ausstellung. Ein Besuch bei Jakob Wothly, *Photographische Correspondenz* II, 1865, p. 164.

Fig. 6 František Fridrich, Prague, Old Town Square, ca. 1868, albumen print, IAH CAS, inv. no. 20679

the standard format 24 × 30 cm (fig. 6). The panoramic effect was only achieved subsequently, by the cropping of the shots in the upper or bottom sections. Fridrich worked in similar fashion (and much more often) also with smaller formats: he used a single camera, approximately of the 10 × 10 cm format, in the production of *cartes de visite* and stereo photographs. Different cut-outs from these shots resulted in both horizontal and vertical *cartes de visite* and stereo views (fig. 7). Exceptionally, the photographs were distributed in the more or less original format (fig. 8b).

Fig. 7 František Fridrich, Prague, Vyšehrad, albumen prints, IAH CAS, inv. nos. 24552, 13763, 24519

Fig. 8 František Fridrich, Prague, Belle-Vue Garden Restaurant, 1864, albumen prints, IAH CAS, (left) inv. no. 20034, (right) s. n.

Although Fridrich was recognised in his time as the most productive Prague photographer with the best equipment, he probably owned neither a panoramic camera, *carte de visite* camera, nor a stereoscopic camera with two lenses. Fridrich's stereographs invariably consist of two individual positives. Some of these shots are created in perfect harmony with the principles of stereoscopy. However, two identical cut-outs were often mounted on one cardboard, and conversely, there are also stereo photographs combining two completely different photos (fig. 9); in this case – it is a combination of two different negatives, but bearing the same inventory number (cf. figs. 10a and 10b; see the inscriptions at the bottom parts).

Fig. 9 František Fridrich, Prague, Old Town Bridge Tower, 21 April 1865, albumen print, IAH CAS, inv. no. 24556

Fig. 10 František Fridrich, Prague, Old Town Bridge Tower, 21 April 1865, albumen prints, *cartes de visite*, IAH CAS, inv. nos. 13344, 11904

The existence of duplicates occasionally makes the situation, or the notions of our knowledge and the course of the history of photography, considerably more complicated. For example, the Prague catalogue involved the issue of the authorship and dating of a photographic series the producer of which was not until then doubted. The photos had been attributed to the Prague bookseller, publisher – and supposedly also photographer – Heinrich Carl Joachim Satow (1839–?), whose water mark is also found on the cardboard.⁵ However, in the course of research for the book of Prague photographs, identical shots started to emerge, in the form of *cartes de visite* and cabinet cards, linked – according to the inscriptions – to a “photographer and publisher Vrba”, of whom or his possible contact with Satow nothing is known (fig. 11). To make the thing even more baffling, a third series of albumen prints of an approximately *carte de visite* format but mounted on an atypical paper layer came to light (fig. 12). It finally transpired that these were illustrations originally pasted in Johann Friedrich Schulz’s book *The Newest Guide through Prague* published by – nobody else than – Carl Satow (fig. 13).⁶ Unlike the first two series, however, these were not prints from original or copy negatives but low-quality reproductions of *cartes de visite* or cabinet cards published earlier under the name of Vrba; some show the original inscription (fig. 12, 13).

Fig. 11 J. Vrba, Prague, Powder Tower, ca. 1865, albumen print, cabinet card, IAH CAS, inv. no. 19327

Fig. 12 [J. Vrba], Prague, Powder Tower, ca. 1865, albumen print, 97×58 / 140×104 mm, IAH CAS, inv. no. 8350

A large number of interesting duplicates emerged during the preparation of the Prague catalogue. A special group among them consists of side-reversed photographs. Judging by the specimens which I have seen, they were mostly created by itinerant photographers who were only active in Prague briefly and, as a result, were more prone to making mistakes when copying the prints. Or – in another case – the photographs were reproductions from glass transparencies (fig. 14), sometimes very likely pirate copies or copies of copies – judging by their quality (fig. 15).

⁵ E.g. Photographic Collection of the Prague City Museum, inv. no. H 173 830.

⁶ John Frederic Schulz, *The Newest Guide through Prague*, Prague 1869. – Johann Friedrich Schulz, *Neuester Führer durch Prag und dessen Umgebungen*, Prague 1870.

Fig. 13a Johann Friedrich Schulz, *Neuester Führer durch Prag und dessen Umgebungen*, Prague 1870, frontispiece, Municipal Library of Prague; figs. 13b–13g [J. Vrba], Prague views, ca. 1869, albumen prints, IAH CAS, samples of illustrations from the book by J. F. Schulz *Neuester Führer durch Prag und dessen Umgebungen*; once bound in the book, today separated and catalogued as individual photographic objects.

Fig. 14 Athanase Clouzard & Charles Soulier / Ferrier père, fils et Soulier, Prague Castle, 1857, later reproduction, lantern slide, private collection

Fig. 15 Athanase Clouzard & Charles Soulier / Mantel & Riedel, Prague Castle, 1857 / 1860s, albumen print, IAH CAS, inv. no. 20074

Collections

As I have mentioned at the beginning, the other area where duplicates play an important part consists of collections, or their management. Duplicates can be found almost everywhere, and it is virtually impossible to ignore them. Sometimes they are sort of invisible both to researchers and curators, at other times they are almost too visible and are considered needless, or even undesired. That is why some of them are discarded, exchanged, catalogued under the same number, or their acquisition is rejected in the first place. This is particularly true of collections that are built

progressively, item by item, and include a reliable cataloguing system. Such collections naturally avoid superficially duplicate objects, accepting perhaps just a single one – as “insurance”, a backup of the “original”, an item for a “preservation collection”, “spare part” or as an item to be exchanged, which is a rule many private collectors stick to, in any area.

On the other hand, there are collections that seem to be self-generating, instant, created through the merging of large, chaotic and possibly or likely related units, which is also the case of the mentioned photographic collection of the IAH (fig. 16). The collection was officially established in 2008, yet its roots go much deeper. It basically contains the photographic material which was in 2008, like graphics and drawings before, deliberately and in a relatively short period of time removed from the estate of art historian Zdeněk Wirth (1878–1961). The estate comprised by manuscripts, prints, photographs, drawings, correspondence, books etc. has been part of the IAH archive since the early 1960s. However, few people knew about the photographs, as there existed no catalogue or inventory.⁷

Fig. 16 Collection of photographs, Documentation Department, IAH CAS; the state in 2008

Zdeněk Wirth himself came to the photographs largely in a way that now appears totally unacceptable. A major part consists of series from the estates of several architects and heritage care specialists whose career trajectories are not exactly known today. In contrast, the provenance of the remaining part – and this is the problematic one – is perfectly clear: these are photographs which Wirth acquired thanks to his involvement in the management of the so called National Cultural Committee, a state body responsible for the cataloguing and provision of art collections confiscated after the Second World War by the Czechoslovak state. These were predominantly family archives of the local, often related, aristocratic families or citizens of German nationality.⁸ It is not known why some of the photographs remained with Zdeněk Wirth and others in archives or chateau depositories – that is in their original homes; nonetheless, the outcome of Wirth’s collecting and research activities is a collection roughly amounting to over 100,000 photographs of all kinds – positives, negatives, transparencies, postcards, from salt paper to gelatine paper, albums, *cartes de visite*,

⁷ Petra Trnková ed., *Oudadate Pix: Revealing a Photographic Archive*, Prague 2010.

⁸ Kristina Uhlíková, *Zdeněk Wirth, první dvě životní etapy (1878–1939)*, Praha 2010. – Cf. Kristina Uhlíková ed., *Konfiszované Schicksale. Kunstdenkmäler aus deutschem Besitz, erworben durch den tschechoslowakischen Staat, und ihre nordböhmisches Besitzer*, Prague 2020.

folios, panoramas, portraits, architecture etc. Plus, at the IAH, there are also photographs, usually albums, which were removed from Wirth's estate much earlier and transferred to the IAH Library where they literally formed a "non-collection" as they did not fit in the library's established cataloguing system, and gradually fell into oblivion.⁹ This vast body of material naturally includes numerous duplicates. To give an idea, out of 700 photographs reproduced in the Prague catalogue approximately 450 come from the IAH collection. For the remaining 250 catalogue items (with a few exceptions) at least one duplicate was identified in the IAH collections.

Despite the fact that only a small part of the IAH photographic collection has been catalogued, we have a relatively good overview of duplicates. Based on the nature of the institution, the art-history or art-historical-topography approach, i.e. filing by locality (and de facto assembling duplicates), was chosen in the first wave of sorting out and cataloguing. This appears a practical solution in the everyday run of the collection. The "dark" side of this approach is that many of the original series have been disturbed and scattered, and it is now extremely difficult to put them back together. The question remains what would have been better; either way, although we have lost something, we have also gained something, especially as regards the study of photographic "practices".

Conclusion

The knowledge of duplicates, possibly across collections and institutions, is vital if we are interested in the history of photography not as a list of names, works and events but as a stream of images, discoveries, ideas, meanings and roles that change over time, intertwine, become stronger, return or completely vanish. However, this makes the curator's job all the more tricky when it comes to drawing up a Disaster Plan. Collection disaster plans usually comprise a chapter on Prioritizing Collections which instructs the staff to make three lists of top priority, medium priority and low priority materials. Of course, it also involves a decision as to where to place duplicates when making a list of priorities. As is known, priorities are typically based on criteria like rareness, uniqueness, originality, monetary value or just being special. Duplicates then usually fall – obviously completely illogically – into a final, bottom category, i.e. among the "replaceable". Yet, there is a hope – it is called "research value". This quality can eventually elevate the status of duplicates and promote them to the top priority level.

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⁹ On the concept of non-collections see primarily Elizabeth Edwards, *The Presence of Non-Collections and the Challenge of Photographic Ecosystems*, published 23.9.2016 in the series [Institutions and the Production of 'Photographs'](https://www.fotomuseum.ch/en/explore/still-searching/articles/29378_the_presence_of_non_collections_and_the_challenge_of_photographic_ecosystems), https://www.fotomuseum.ch/en/explore/still-searching/articles/29378_the_presence_of_non_collections_and_the_challenge_of_photographic_ecosystems. – Elizabeth Edwards, *Thoughts on the "Non-Collections" of the Archival Ecosystem*, in Julia Bärnighausen, Costanza Caraffa, Stefanie Klamm, Franka Schneider, and Petra Wodtke eds., *Photo-Objects: On the Materiality of Photographs and Photo Archives*, Berlin 2019, pp. 67–82, [<https://www.mprl-series.mpg.de/studies/12/4/index.html#fn1>].